

PEDAGOGICAL BASES OF DEVELOPING COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE OF FUTURE TEACHERS

Sherzod Primov

(PhD)

Teacher of Jizzakh state pedagogical university

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7981703>

Annotation: The article provides feedback on the pedagogical foundations of developing communicative competence of future teachers. The content of pedagogical disciplines is aimed at developing the humane basis of communicative competence of students of pedagogical institutions.

Key words: communicative competence, communicative skills, vocational interest motivation, vocational conversation.

Increasing the status of teachers in the United Nations Convention on Education, Science and Culture and the Convention on Technical and Vocational Education and the Convention on the Elimination of Discrimination in Education, on the Importance of Educational, Scientific and Cultural Content. In addition, much attention has been paid to the development of communicative competence of teachers based on international qualifications. In the world, it is important to create equal conditions for the quality of education for teachers and students of higher education institutions, to exchange experience and to promote their communicative competence, to pay attention to the introduction of innovative pedagogical technologies in the educational process.

Large-scale reforms in the country provide a great opportunity for young people to actively interact with their peers abroad in the fields of science, culture, entrepreneurship, sports and other areas, to demonstrate their potential worldwide. In the Strategy of actions for further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2017-2021 "one of the main priorities for comprehensive development of higher education is" continuous improvement of the quality and level of professionalism of teachers".

Of all these, we pursue one common goal - it has been emphasized that Uzbekistan has to be competitive in the world in the field of science, intellectual potential, modern personnel, high technologies. The development of the communicative competence of future teachers in higher education institutions necessitated an improvement in the globalization process.

One of the conditions for the development of communicative competence of a future teacher is the formation of humanistic communication skills in it. We

believe that the content of pedagogical disciplines can contribute to the development of a communicative humanitarian framework for a future teacher.

Therefore, the content of psycho-pedagogical training becomes the subject of special attention. It relates to the state educational standards in the field of pedagogy, the choice of disciplines in the qualification requirements, the logic, the consistency of the study of psycho-pedagogical disciplines. Much has been said about the elimination of duplication of material in the various disciplines, the amount of student workloads, and the organization of their independent work.

Almost all experts say that the nomenclature of pedagogical sciences is not logical, and their content does not reflect the current state of theoretical research in pedagogy and education. It is necessary to consider the state educational standards in the field of pedagogy in higher education institutions, the issues related to personal education in teaching the subject of psycho-pedagogical preparation in the qualification requirements, the philosophy of education as a whole, and the principles of humanity of the educational process. Some issues are limited by the technology level (technology of interaction, technology of self-development).

There is plenty of room for different types of control (diagnostic, intermediate, current, final), but as one of the ways to humanize the relationship between the teacher and the student, the issue of self-control and self-control as manifestations of subjective situations in the learning and learning process have not been released.

Pedagogical communication is viewed as a whole, separate from the educational process. Personal qualities of professional significance, pedagogical skills, pedagogical situation, professional knowledge and skills, pedagogical communication are revealed on pedagogical theories, systems, technologies, access to pedagogical profession.

At the same time, based on numerous research materials on pedagogical activity, the personal qualities of the teacher are important in the direct pedagogical communication between the teacher and the student, his or her pedagogical position (which must be humane in all teachers), professional skills and it is worth noting that the list of skills consists almost entirely of communicative skills and skills.

Thus, the existing opportunities for pedagogical sciences to develop the humane basis of the communicative competence and communicative competence of the future teacher are not fully utilized.

At the same time, the humanitarian communicative competence of the pedagogue person determines the nature of the teacher's interactions with the students and the basis of his or her communicative competence.

The orientation of the content of pedagogical disciplines to the development of the humane basis of the communicative competence of students of pedagogical higher education institutions contributes to the development of its communicative competence.

The humanistic communicative orientation of the child implies that the teacher understands the spirituality and uniqueness of each individual. Therefore, the main task of teaching pedagogical subjects is to prepare the future teacher for perceptions of students as impartial and equal subjects [3]. But the future teacher must realize that true equality in relationships is not the same for everyone.

Therefore, the key role must be in cultivating the ability to see and appreciate each individual's individuality, to develop their ability to care and sympathize, in other words, to develop student-centered communication in the humanities.

The need to develop the communicative competence of a future teacher based on a person-centered education arises not only as a human being and a child, but also because the future teacher may face a number of dimensions that exist in the modern school.

The modern concept of pedagogical education focuses on two tasks. Develop a humane, emotional-value orientation on this student. Development of the communicative competence of the future teacher will provide a high level of communicative competence of the teacher and the success of his professional career.

It is legitimate to view the theory of education as a precise level of human theory. Understanding its role and status, its value and function is linked to the interpretation of parenting, the nature of the teacher's interaction with children [4].

There is nothing in human existence other than human creation, and therefore man is a subject of social existence. But not as one, but as a participant in vertical and horizontal social relations. The subjectivity of a person is in the relationship, through that interaction.

Such an issue (as the caring child is supposed to be) is necessary because not every human being is considered humane. Humanism envisions the subject as a subject.

Thus, the content of this particular discipline has a greater potential for the development of the human communicative competence of the teacher than the normative subjects in pedagogy. For example, in all of the topics discussed, the individual-oriented, humanitarian aspects of the teacher's interactions with children are at the forefront.

The content of the special subject "Teacher's communicative competence" developed by us is defined as one of the conditions for communicative competence of the future teacher, directly contributing to the development of the humane basis of his her personal communicative competence. Such orientation of the future teacher to the development of humanitarian communicative competence of the future teacher facilitates the development of his communicative competence, which was influenced by the results of our experimental work.

References:

1. UNESCO international regulatory documents. //The responsible editor of the Uzbek edition L.Saidova. -T; Justice, 2004, pp. 19-62.
2. The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 7, 2017 N UP-4947 "On the strategy of further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan".
3. Bushelova B.V. Cultura obshcheniya.- Petropalovsk, 1990
4. Gusinsky EN, Turchaninova Yu.I. The image of the image. -M., 1994

